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ASSESSMENT OF GENERAL OCULAR HEALTH AND VISUAL STATUS OF THE SMALL-SCALE INDUSTRIAL WORKERS

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND:

Incidence of visual disorders in industrial workers may result in visual loss, anguish, reduced manpower, man hours and economic loss. Most of these hazards are preventable if adequate precautionary measures are taken. [8,11] Worker's eyes may be exposed to a variety of dangerous agents depending on the type of industry which may constitute an occupational hazard. According to OSHA, personal protective equipment is devices design to protect workers' eyes from severe work place injury or illness resulting from contact with metal splash, chemical splash, dust, flying particle or radiation. [14,16] So the aim of the study is to assess Ocular Health, Visual & Refractive status of the workers working in the metal machinery (small scale) industries.

METHODS:

A clinical examination of the workers was accompanied by detailed occupational history in the small scale & tiny sector metal machinery industries. Visual acuity was measured using Snellen's chart for distance and N notation reading chart for near. Color vision testing was done with Pseudoisochromatic-Ishihara chart. Anterior segment of eye was examining with the help of torch light and SLE. Fundus evaluation was done with the help of direct ophthalmoscope. Objective & Subjective Refraction was performed using Retinoscope and trial case. Stereopsis was measured with the help of Titmus Fly test.

RESULTS:

Hundred and eighty small scale industry workers were screened. Among them, all were male with a mean age (45.5 ± 11.31 years). 74% showed Visual impairment. The most common visual disorders were uncorrected presbyopia 65% (117), uncorrected refractive error 59% (106) out of which 17% (30) were already use their own spectacle prescription remaining 42% (76) were prescribed new spectacle. Color vision defect was found in 2% (3). Out of hundred and eighty only 11% (19) of the workers were use protective eye wear, remaining 89% (161) of them were never use protective eye wears on daily basis.

CONCLUSION:

This study concluded that uncorrected refractive error and uncorrected presbyopia was high among workers as they are not aware about eye health and safety measures for the occupation. The use of safety eye devices is low among workers and recommends that process about awareness and implementation of ocular safety in these industries is established as occupational protective measures are important for metal machinery industrial workers who are at a high risk of eye injuries. It is recommended that, there is a need to review the design, and reinforce the strict implementation of occupational eye safety programs.

KEY WORDS:

Visual acuity, Refractive error, Presbyopia, Industrial workers, Fundus, Stereopsis, Color vision, Personal Protective Equipment

INTRODUCTION

India at present is considered a key power and is revolving into an established country from a rural country; an enormous division of its people still belongs to the poverty line. In emerging countries, great struggles are focused towards the development of small-scale industries as these are considered the engine for their economic growth.^[2]

Defective vision is quiet challenging which is detected after a long period of continuous exposure to the surroundings.

It is assumed that Incidence of visual disorders in industrial workers may result in visual loss, anguish, reduced manpower, man hours and economic loss. Most of these hazards are preventable if adequate precautionary measures are taken.^[8,11] Worker's eyes may be exposed to a variety of dangerous agents depending on the type of industry which may constitute an occupational hazard.^[12,13] Most of the reported studies related to non-traumatic ocular disorders that have emerged from developed countries with relatively little information from developing countries such as India.^[10]

According to WHO, over 1000 million people worldwide are employed in small-scale industries, the engineering industry of India is one such industry. It is an unorganized sector, mostly run by private formations. It provides employment chiefly for men mostly from uneducated and poor background.^[15]

The workers of this industry hardly ever benefit from industrial health-and-safety requirements. As a result, their health suffers; studies show diseases of the eye, accidents, injuries, skin diseases, stress, insomnia, etc. The ill health is compounded by various socioeconomic factors such as poverty, lack of education, poor working conditions, excess working hours, and poor diet.^[14,18] Uncorrected refractive errors often lead to eye injuries in industrial workers. There is yet neither literature existing in our country on the quantity of visual impairment in industrial workers nor any data to compare eye injuries due to the deprived visual status of the injured.^[14,18]

This study is a try to file the visual and refractive status of industrial workers as the first step to determine the eye care needs of the industrial workers and to frame an industrial eye safety program.

According to OSHA, personal protective equipment is devices design to protect workers' eyes from severe work place injury or illness resulting from contact with metal splash, chemical splash, dust, flying particle or radiation.^[14,16]

Basically, there are PPE used for protection of the eye for hazard. That protective device includes Spectacle, Goggles, Face shield, Helmet with each of these being develop for a particular task. It involves Safety Spectacle, Impact cup (chipping)Goggles, dust Goggles, Chemical Goggles, Welding Goggles, Welding Helmet, Face Shield, High impact Personal Protective Goggles.^[15]

PURPOSE

The purpose of the study is to assess Ocular Health, Visual & Refractive status of the workers working in the metal machinery (small scale) industries.

It includes:

- A. Anterior & Posterior segment of eye
- B. Visual acuity
- C. Refractive error
- D. Visual field
- E. Color vision

F. Stereopsis**MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY**

A cross-sectional randomize study was conducted in the small scale and tiny sector metal machinery industries in Ahmedabad industrial area within a period of November 2019-January 2021. Authorization for study taken from management of the metal machinery industries selected. One hundred and Eighty (180) workers were participated in the study. Subjects were enrolled in study after obtaining the informed consent. In addition to demographic data, detailed occupational history was asked.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Technical workers of the industries 2. Workers who are willing to participate

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Non-technical workers of the industry
2. Workers who are not willing to participate
3. Workers with intellectual and cognitive disabilities

MATERIALS:

Following instruments were used in this study:

- Pen-Torch
- Portable Slit –lamp Biomicroscope
- Direct –Ophthalmoscope
- Retinoscope
- Snellen’s distance and near visual acuity charts
- Trial case
- Titmus Fly test
- Ishihara pseudo-isochromatic plates
- Occluder
- Pin hole

METHODOLOGY:

- Torch light examination was done with a pen–torch & portable slit lamp to rule out any anterior segment abnormalities and pupillary function and defects.
- Presenting visual acuity was measured using Snellen’s visual acuity chart for distance placed at six meters with adequate illumination. Each eye was tested separately with and without glasses where applicable and subsequently refracted using retinoscope to rule out any refractive error objectively if their visual acuity less than normal (6/6, 6/9). Subjective refraction was performed using trial case which contains trial frame, lenses, occluder & pinhole.
- Near visual acuity was tested using N Notation reading chart. Near correction was given to those who have near visual acuity less than N6 to rule out presbyopia.
- Color vision was tested using the Ishihara pseudo-isochromatic plates and finding noted as normal or abnormal (Red green deficiency).
- Fundus evaluation was done using direct of ophthalmoscope.
- Stereopsis was measured with the help of Titmus Fly test.
- Visual field measurement was done using confrontation test.
- Cover test was performed to rule out whether phoria or tropia is present or not. Ocular motility was also noted in each and every subject.

RESULTS GRAPH: 01

Out of the total number of 180 workers all workers were male. The workers were aged between 19-79 years with a mean age of (45.20 ± 11.311) years. The workers age was categorized as 19-29 were 31 (17%), 30-39 were 26 (15%), 40-49 were 49 (27%), 50-59 were 43 (24%), 60-69 were 25 (14%) and 70-79 were 6 (3%). The majority of the workers were aged between 40-49.

Out of 180 workers, 168(93%) workers were working for 8 hours/day, while 12 (7%) workers were working for 12 hours/day.

GRAPH: 03

Out of 180 workers, only 19 (11%) workers were preferring to use safety goggles on daily basis remaining 161 (89%) workers were never use safety goggles.

GRAPH: 04

For Right eye(OD) ,Out of 180 workers 110 (61.11%) of the workers had normal anterior segment, while 42 (23.33%) of the workers had cataractous changes , 43(23.889%) of the workers had age related arcus senilis, 19 (10.556%) of the workers had undergone cataract surgery ,3 (1.667%) of the workers had pterygium, 1(0.556%) of the workers had conjunctival congestion, 1 (0.556%) of the workers had lid swelling, 2 (1.112%) of the workers had blebs, 1 (0.556%) of the workers had pinguecula, 1(0.556%) of the workers had mild ptosis.

GRAPH: 05

For Left eye (OS), Out of 180 workers,110 (61.112%) of the workers had normal anterior segment, 40 (22.223%) of the workers had cataractous changes, 41 (22.778%) of the workers had age related arcus senilis, 20 (11.112%) of the workers had undergone cataract surgery, 6

(3.334%) of the workers had pterygium, 1 (0.556%) of the workers had conjunctival congetion, 6a, 2(1.112%) of the workers had mild ptosis, 1 (0.556%) of the workers had corneal haze.

GRAPH: 06

Out of 180 workers, 80% workers were had normal posterior segment & 20% workers were experienced fundus abnormalities.

GRAPH: 07

For Right eye (OD), Out of 180 workes, 40 (22.223%) of the workers had normal vision (6/6), 109 (60.556%) of the workers had mild impairment of vision (6/9-6/18), 22 (12.223%) of the workers had moderate impairment of vision (6/24-6/36), 5 (2.778%) of the workers had severe impairment of vision (6/60), while remaining 4 (2.223%) of the workers had very poor vision (CF) Without correction.

Out of 180 workes, 75 (41.667%) of the workers had normal vision (6/6), 96 (53.334%) of the workers had mild impairment of vision (6/9-6/18), 4 (2.223%) of the workers had moderate

impairment of vision (6/24-6/36),2 (1.112%) of the workers had severe impairment of vision (6/60), while remaining 3(1.667%) of the workers had very poor vision (CF) With correction.

GRAPH: 08

For Left eye (OS), Out of 180 workes,47 (26.112%) of the workers had normal vision (6/6),105 (58.334%) of the workers had mild impairment of vision (6/9-6/18),20 (11.112%) of the workers had moderate impairment of vision (6/24-6/36),4 (2.223%) of the workers had severe impairment of vision (6/60), while remaining 4 (2.223%) of the workers had very poor vision (CF) Without correction.

Out of 180 workes,77 (42.778%) of the workers had normal vision (6/6),97 (53.889%) of the workers had mild impairment of vision (6/9-6/18),1 (0.556%) of the workers had moderate impairment of vision (6/24-6/36),1 (0.556%) of the workers had severe impairment of vision (6/60), while remaining 4 (2.223%) of the workers had very poor vision (CF) With correction.

GRAPH: 9

Out of 180 workers, 74% of the workers had refractive error. Above figure shows distribution of the presenting refractive error status. After correction 23% of the workers have hyperopia, 29% of the workers have myopia and 22% of the workers have astigmatism, while remaining 26% of the workers were found emmetropic.

GRAPH: 10

Out of 180 workers, 29% of the workers were found myopic. Above figure shows myopia classified based on their degree as low, moderate and high.

For Right eye (OD), 30(20%) of the workers had very low myopia (0.25D-1.00D), 15(8.334%) of the workers had low myopia (1.25D-2.00D), 8(4.445%) of the workers had moderate-high myopia (2.50D-8.00D).

For Left eye (OS), 30(20%) of the workers had very low myopia (0.25D-1.00D), 19(10.556%) of the workers had low myopia (1.25D-2.00D), 7(3.889%) of the workers had moderate-high myopia (2.50D-8.00D).

GRAPH: 11

Out of 180 workers, 23% of the workers were found hyperopic. Above figure shows myopia classified based on their degree as low, moderate and high.

For Right eye (OD), 29(16.112%) of the workers had very low hyperopia (0.25D-1.00D), 13(7.223%) of the workers had moderate-hyperopia (1.25D-2.00D), 6(3.334%) of the workers had high hyperopia (2.50D-6.00D).

For Left eye (OS), 28(15.556%) of the workers had very low hyperopia (0.25D-1.00D), 12(6.667%) of the workers had low hyperopia (1.25D-2.00D), 7(3.889%) of the workers had moderate-high hyperopia (2.50D-6.00D).

GRAPH: 12

Out of 180 workers, 117 (65%) of the workers were presbyopia with uncorrected presbyopia, who required glasses for near vision, remaining 63 (35%) of the workers were non presbyopia.

GRAPH: 13

Above figure shows distribution of the presenting presbyopia correction with respect to worker's age.

Out of 180 workers, 1(0.556%) of the worker was corrected with +0.75D, 15(8.334%) of the workers were with +1.00D, 14(7.778%) of the workers were corrected with +1.25D, 13(7.223%) of the workers were corrected with +1.50D, 4(2.223%) of the workers were corrected with +1.75D, 17(9.445%) of the workers were corrected with +2.00, 20(11.112%) of the workers were corrected with +2.25D, 22(12.223%) of the workers were corrected with +2.50D, 9(5%) of the workers were corrected with +2.75D, 8(4.445%) of the workers were corrected with +3.00D, 1(0.556%) of the workers were corrected with +3.50D

GRAPH: 14

Out of 180 workers, 74(41%) of the workers were there to whom spectacle correction was not given, 106 (59%) of the workers were there to whom spectacle correction was given. Out of 106(59%) of the workers to whom spectacle correction was given, 76 (42%) of the workers were already wear their own spectacle correction –new correction was prescribing to them, while 30(17%) of the workers were given new spectacle correction-they never wore spectacle before.

GRAPH: 15

Among 180 individuals who had their color vision assessed, 177 (98%) of them were normal and 3(2%) were abnormal. Out of 3, 1 was welder, 1 was machine operator and 1 was buffing. The significance of color vision abnormality is not known as the small-scale workers were not aware about the defect. Occupations versus color vision were not statistically significant.

GRAPH: 16

Out of 180 workers, 2 ((1.112%) of the workers had 20 sec. of arc stereopsis,6 (3.334%) of the workers had 40 sec. of arc, 11 (6.112%) of the workers had 50 sec. of arc, 16(8.889%) of the workers had 60sec. of arc, 11 (6.112%) of the workers had 80 sec. of arc, 20 (11.112%) of the workers had 100 sec. of arc, 5 (2.778%) of the workers had 140 sec. of arc, 38(21.112%) of the workers had 200 sec. of arc, 29 (16.112%) of the workers had 400 sec. of arc,19 (10.556%) of the workers had 800 sec. of arc,1 (0.556%) of the workers had 3000 sec. of arc, while 22

(12.223%) of the workers had no stereopsis. 39.449% of the workers had fine stereoacuity, 37.224% of the workers had moderate stereoacuity, 11.1116% of the workers had coarse stereoacuity, while 12.223% of the workers had nil stereoacuity

GRAPH: 17

180 workers were included in the study, out of that 119(66.112%) of the workers were managed with spectacle correction remaining 61(33.889%) of the workers either wear spectacle or no need for it. 161(89.445%) of the workers were advised to use safety goggles (PPE) during working hours, while remaining 19(10.556%) of the workers were already use PPE. 48(26.667%) of the workers were further refer to hospital for detailed eye examination.

DISSCUSION

Apart from the domestic environment, the workplace is the set where several people spend a large proportion of their time. This study falls under the monarchy of occupational vision which is concerned with the efficient and safe visual functioning of an individual within the work environment [20]. The small-scale industry workers voluntarily participated in the study. The convenient sampling method was used because we had inadequate right to access to the workers so we could manage to assess the visual and refractive status of all the workers who participated in our study at one particular location. Visual examinations were carried out as in previous studies. The results obtained were within the areas of research in other parts of the world. The mean age of workers in the study was 45.2 ± 11.311 years. This is higher than that found in related 6 industrial establishments in Saharanpur, India which was 35.3 years, $11 \pm 23.0 \pm 6.0$ years found in miners in Turkey 12 and 33.4 ± 12.0 years found in the study of occupationally injured workers in Tubingen, Germany, 39.7 years found in Ambattur Industrial Estate, Chennai.

In this study the majority of the occupations listed were Fabrication fitter followed by Machine operator, helper, Grinding operator, and engineers. This shows that only the owners of the small-scale industries were more interested to undergo visual examination than their employees because of the lack of time in the working environment.

The existing research also supports to create base line data on the visual status of industrial workers indicates that by a majority 75 (41.667%) of workers have normal visual acuity (6/6). There are 93 individuals (53.334%) who come under a fairly poor distance vision range of 6/9 to 6/18 and 4 workers (2.223%) who have poor visual acuity ranging from 6/24 to 6/36 and 5 workers (2.778%) have very poor visual acuity ranging from 6/60 to CF who come under

category 1 of the WHO grades of visual impairment ^[14] if their vision is left uncorrected. Significant visual impairment was observed in 21.8% individuals and moderate impairment in 34.5% of cases was found by Rajiv Desai et al. ^[16] in his study conducted in India in the year 1990. Significant visual impairment was observed in 6.3% individual and moderate impairment in 17.1% of workers was found by Salai dhavamathi janarthan et al. ^[2] in his study conducted in Chennai, India in year 2017.

The occurrence of uncorrected refractive error was 59% in this study. (out of which 42% of the workers wear their own spectacle correction while remaining 17% of the workers do not wear) This value is higher than the 56.7% found by Titiyal et al. in six industrial establishments at Saharanpur in India in the year 1998 ^[23] much higher than 36.93% found by Salai dhavamathi janarthan et al. at Chennai, India in 2017^[2], also higher than the selected industrial establishments (cement factory, mining, saw mill and steel works) in Enugu, Nigeria ^[10] where only 26.2% was found in that study. This does not prove that uncorrected refractive errors can cause eye diseases in factory workers because our data is too small to represent an industrial workforce of 90.1 million in the country ^[26] and a further survey to be conducted in the future. Presbyopia was observed in 65% of the population. Out of 180 workers, 117 of the workers could not read paper prints at 40 cm (presbyopia), yet none of them had their near prescription. Remaining 35% of the workers were non-presbyopia. In Ambattur Industrial Estate, Chennai, Presbyopia was observed in 53% of the population. 37% of the workers could not read paper prints at 40 cm (presbyopia) by Salai Dhavamathi Janarthan et al. ^[2] Hence, this had the potential to place the workers at risk of injuring themselves and the fellow workers. Most of the workers reported not wearing their spectacle correction because there were not aware about the near correction requirement and also no readily available eye care service at the tiny sector industries.

Color vision was normal in 98% of the workers while, 2% of the workers were observed abnormal (red-green deficiency). Occupations versus color vision were not statistically significant. We also observed that no similar studies showed a higher percentage in color vision. This was an unusual finding, in the future we recommend to focus the study on effect of functioning of industry workers, if they are color blind.

It was observed that 39.449% of the workers had fine stereoacuity, 37.224% of the workers had moderate stereoacuity, 11.116% of the workers had coarse stereoacuity, while 12.223% of the workers had nil stereoacuity, although there is no significance of stereopsis with occupation and age was found. It was observed that 80% of the workers had normal fundus, and 20% of the workers were found with abnormal fundus whose age was observed above 50.

The eye diseases observed in this study were common to those found in other industrial establishments in other parts of the world. The occurrence of cataract, arcus senilis, pterygium, conjunctival congestion, lid swelling, blebs, pinguecula, mild ptosis and corneal haze were 23.33%, 23.889%, 1.667%, 0.556%, 0.556%, 1.112%, 0.553%, 0.556%, 0.556% respectively. The finding that the 89% of the workers were not wear protective glasses while, 11% of the workers were use occasionally or routinely, were comparable to the study findings by Titiyal and Murthy in India where 96.4% ^[23] of the workers did not use protective eye devices. The reasons given for not using ocular protective devices were not questioned due to lack of time and hence this can be continued in the future and which would definitely increase cases of industrial ocular injuries. It has been reported that work related eye injuries (WREI) are more common among workers in metal work and machinery industries ^[7].

In recent times, the impact of poor environmental conditions at the workplace, lack of awareness of work conditions, and presence of adverse health conditions in workers has received much attention. The environment of workplaces differs and hence the contributing factor of work-related injury and illness also varies; identification of the responsible factors in any specific work environment would help in clarifying the etiology and would also be useful

for prevention and containment of occupation-related ill health. Our study concludes that Refractive errors and eye injuries may be reduced by better education of the workers about risky behaviours and by persuading them to comply with correcting spectacles and safety measures.

Key Benefits of Eye Examination & Vision Screening

- Gives employees a convenient way to have a vision exam.
 - Provides education about eye health
 - Can address vision-related problems by generating a prescription for corrective lenses
 - Discusses preventative methods of minimizing eye strain and the possible resulting headaches.
- Both employers and employees have praised Eye examination & vision screenings. On the employer side, it's a way to promote eye health within the industries. Good eye health of the workers leads to smooth working environment of the industries which results in the higher productivity rate.

On the employee side, almost every participant left the screening more knowledgeable about how to maintain eye health. Additionally, vision exams can help uncover refractive errors and address them. Overall, this contributes to, not only productivity in the work place, but to the employee's positive view of the company as well.

CONCLUSION

From this study, it was concluded that the presenting visual status of small-scale industry workers maintain their safety and that of their fellow workers. Uncorrected refractive error and presbyopia were common among these workers due to the non-availability of eye care services and also, they are not aware about eye health and safety measures for the occupation. It is observed that Refractive errors and eye injuries may be reduced by better education of the workers about risky behaviors and by persuading them to comply with correcting spectacles and safety measures. Occupational protective measures are important for metal machinery workers who are at high risk of eye injuries. It is suggested that prior to job placement all workers undergo eye examination, cover test, visual field, color vision, stereopsis, fundus examination, vision screening and get their refractive errors rectified. We in future suggest that an industrial eye health and safety surveillance system should be recognized to monitor the occurrence of eye diseases and injuries. It should also be tasked to undertake eye risk assessment in such industries to control inevitable work-related eye disorders. The benefit of vision screening is having a workforce that can be more productive because of a decrease in vision related disturbances. It also provides education to the workers about Eye health. Overall, eye examination and vision screening contribute to, not only productivity in the work place, but to the employee's positive view of the company as well. The use of personal protective equipment's is low in these workers and suggests that, measures to implement ocular safety should be undertaken in these industries, there is a need to review the design, and reinforce the strict implementation of occupational eye safety programs.

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